

Guide to Developing a Research Data Management Plan-DMP

Introduction:

"Research Data Management Plans" (DMPs) are tools established in the "Data Management Guidelines" implemented by the Vice-Rectorate for Research and Innovation. This plan outlines all relevant aspects of data management and the treatment of data during and after the research process, ensuring that the data are accurate, complete, reliable, and secure.

Research teams at UCA are responsible for creating and updating the plan, as it is part of the documentation required for funding applications. Once the process is completed, the final version of the plan will be submitted. The plan is divided into the following sections: general information about the research, data description, data and documentation quality, data accessibility and reuse, and ethical and legal requirements. Each section includes various items with explanations on how to complete them.

The final research data described in the plan will be deposited in ***Micelio, Plataforma para la investigación UCA***, under the "Databases" entity. This content must include the appropriate Creative Commons license, selecting the option that allows for the greatest data sharing and reuse among researchers and university departments.

This platform is exclusively accessible to the research community and is managed by the Vice-Rectorate for Research and Innovation. Micelio, UCA's research platform, meets the technical and technological recommendations and requirements to ensure that the deposited information and files are interoperable and preserved, thus facilitating visibility, access, impact, and reuse of the data for future research.

Research Data Management Plan (RDMP)

1. GENERAL INFORMATION ABOUT THE RESEARCH

1.1 Research Title:	Title of the Research (Arial, bold, 12 pt)
1.2 Funding Source:	Example: UCA Research Fund
1.3 Research Line / Social Projection Agenda:	Technological Development and Innovation
1.4 Research Code:	FUCA-2023-01
1.5 Research Team: (Identify each author with the following information)	<p>1. Coordinador/a de Investigación</p> <p>Research Coordinator Carlos Armando Alfaro Hernández Teacher Department of Engineering Universidad Centroamericana José Simeón Cañas ORCID:0000-0000-0000-0000 El Salvador</p> <p>Researcher Germán Alejandro Arce Maravilla Industrial Engineer Department of Engineering Universidad Centroamericana José Simeón Cañas ORCID:0000-0000-0000-0000 El Salvador</p> <p>Researcher Julio César López Alfaro Archivist CRAI-Biblioteca "P. Florentino Idoate S.J." Universidad Centroamericana José Simeón Cañas ORCID:0000-0000-0000-0000 El Salvador</p>
1.6 Primary Contact Information:	carmandoh@uca.edu.sv 2020-6060 (Institucional Phone)
1.7 Research Start and End Dates:	Dates: 2023-01-31 a 2024-11-30

1.8 DMP Review Control:	Version 1.0, 13/08/2023 Version 1.1, 24/11/2023 Version 2.0, 15/03/2024
1.9 Data Management Responsible:	Carlos Armando Alfaro Hernández Research Coordinator
2. DATA DESCRIPTION	
2.1 Brief description of the types of data to be generated or collected in the research:	Qualitative data will be generated in audio format, derived from semi-structured interviews with migrants (indigenous youth emigrants, immigrants from Spain, migrant domestic workers, agricultural seasonal workers) and key informants. The estimated total number of interviews is 115.
2.2 Will existing data from UCA research or other sources be used? How will they be used? Under what license are the reused data?	Anonymized microdata from secondary statistical sources prepared by the National Institute of Statistics (INE) will be used: Municipal Register of Inhabitants, Statistics of Residential Variations, Register of Spaniards Residing Abroad, Population and Housing Census 2021. These are public data available for open access.
2.3 What types of formats will the research data have?	XLSX and CSV: tabulation of survey results WAV: interview audios JPEG: photographs from interviews
2.4 What is the estimated volume or size of the data?	5 GB, with a gradual growth estimated at 20% during the research cycle.
3. DATA QUALITY AND DOCUMENTATION	
3.1 How will data consistency and quality be ensured?	Data quality will be ensured through repeated and comparative measurements, compliance with standards for data recording, the use of controlled vocabularies and standard terminology, methodological characterization of measurement configurations, and validation of the collected data. Other quality assurance processes will include providing test results along with the data and peer review of publications based on the data.

3.2 What documentation will accompany the data for interpretation or reuse?	Transcriptions of the interviews (audio files) will be properly anonymized, reviewed, and made available in PDF format. The data corpus will be accompanied by a metadata document (in PDF) that includes a description of the data, notes, contextual information, as well as a unique identifier for each transcription. Each transcription will include a cover page with details such as the date and location of the interview and basic and vague information (to protect anonymity) of the interviewed person.
4. DATA ACCESSIBILITY AND REUSE	
4.1 Of all the data described in section 2 of this DMP, which will be selected and deposited in Micelio, Plataforma para la investigación UCA, for accessibility and reuse? (complete data lifecycle)	Priority will be given to storing the audios obtained from the interviews and files of survey result tabulations. Data will be made visible in <i>Micelio, Plataforma para la investigación UCA</i> , once the article derived from this research has been published in the journal.
4.2 What type of software and/or hardware will be used to visualize the data?	Data Creation in AutoCAD https://acortar.link/J6cKdU Visualization: DWG FastView will be required (this is a free online DWG viewer and editor that is easy and fast for viewing and editing CAD drawings) https://en.dwgfastview.com/
4.3 Which group of researchers, research line, or UCA social projection agenda will find these data useful?	UCA Research Line: 6. Migration
5. ETHICAL AND LEGAL REQUIREMENTS	
5.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that may affect data sharing? How should personal data be handled?	The personal data of the interviewed individuals will be anonymized as a protective measure, with the exception of: María Dolores José Peralta Ivonne de Mangandi Consent was obtained to publicly disclose only their names and photographs due to the nature of

	<p>the research; this information is held by the coordinator.</p> <p>In the case of photos capturing images of minors, their faces will be censored, and they will be deposited in the Micelio Repository with the pixelated effect maintained.</p>
5.2 If UCA's Research Ethics Committee evaluated the research, what aspects of the review affect the use and publication of the research data?	Take into account the committee's ruling and mention the committee's recommendation regarding whether it is appropriate to make the research dataset public in Micelio, the research platform, or if there are considerations that would prevent it
5.3 Are there any restrictions on accessing the data?	Access to the files that will be published in the Data Repository is restricted. Example